

Unusual Effect of the Degree of Cure of some Epoxy Resins on the Compressive Strength of Continuous Fibre Composites

ANALYTICAL MODEL

UNDERSTANDING
ESTIMATING

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Context

Epoxy composites – Automated Fibre Placement - CFRP

Compressive failure of hydrofoils in bending

$$X_c < X_t$$

Compressive strength is a key design parameter

Fibre micro-buckling mechanism

Process

Fibre misalignment

Material

UD non-linear shear behaviour

[Mechin, PhD (2017)]

Estimation of compressive strength requires knowledge of the non-linear shear behaviour of the ply

Common opinion on curing thermosets CFRP

« For best mechanical performance, complete curing is sought »

TYPICAL CURE TIME & TEMPERATURES

0.3°C (0.5°F)/min should be considered the minimum ramp rate. Alternative cure cycles and processes can be used.

PROPERTY	70°C CURE (158°F)	80°C CURE (176°F)	120°C CURE (248°F)	TEST STANDARD
Processing Method	Vacuum Bag / Autoclave	Vacuum Bag / Autoclave	Vacuum Bag / Autoclave	
Typical Ramp Rate	0.3 – 2°C/minute	0.3 – 2°C/minute	0.3 – 2°C/minute	-
Cure Time	12 hrs*	6hrs*	45 minutes*	-
Cure Pressure	-1 Bar / +6 Bar	-1 Bar / +6 Bar	-1 Bar / +6 Bar	-
Dry Tg (DMA)	85°C	98°C	125°C	ASTM D7028

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

CURED RESIN PROPERTIES

Resin cast oven cured for 12 hours at 70°C (158°F). Mean values.

PROPERTY	SYMBOL	UNIT	12 HOURS @ 70 °C (158°F)	6 HOURS @ 80°C (176°F)	45 MINUTES @ 120°C (248°F)	TEST STANDARD
Cured resin density	ρ_{cured}	g/cm ³	1.19	1.19	1.19	Archimedeian principle
Tensile Strength	σ_T	MPa	68	82	83	ISO 527-2
Tensile Modulus	E_T	GPa	3.8	3.4	3.0	ISO 527-2
Flexural Strength	σ_F	MPa	117	123	117	ISO 178
Flexural Modulus	E_F	GPa	3.8	3.5	2.9	ISO 178
Compressive Yield Strength	σ_C	MPa	147	140	117	ISO 604

[Se75 data sheet, Gurit (2022)]

Stiffness decreases when cross-linking increases!

Objective

Stiffness decreases when cross-linking increases

Questions

Q1 - Estimation of consequences on X_c

Q3 - Origins

Q2 - Experimental confirmation

Can we predict the influence of curing on the compressive strength?

Our methodology for compression

UD non-linear shear behaviour

- Fibre anisotropic elastic properties
- Matrix non-linear behaviour
- Arrangement of fibres

Estimation/Validation/Measurement

[Mechin, COST (2023)]

Mechanisms

- UD shear behaviour
- Initial fibre misalignment

Manufacturing defects

- Initial fibre misalignment

Measurement

[Yurgartis, CSTE (1987)]

Estimation/Validation Compressive strength

- Material: ply scale
- Manufacturing defects
- Structural effect : laminate scale

From scale II to scale III

[Mechin et al., COST (2023)]

From scale III to scale IV

[Budiansky, JMPS (1993)]

Influence of the resin behaviour on the compressive strength of the ply

**Can we validate the propagation
from the neat cast resin to the
composite laminate?**

Neat cast resin Se75 Gurit

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$$T_g^\infty = 125^\circ\text{C}$$

II

Tape prepreg with Hexcel IM (IM2C) carbon fibres

III

10 mm

IV

Three scales: resin (II), lamina (III), laminate (IV)

Curing

(DOC) Degrees of conversion (w.r.t. uncured prepregs) – 92%, 95%, 100%

Neat cast resin

II

Lamina

III

Laminate

IV

[Keryvin et al., CPB (2024)]

Same DOC (~1%) at all scales – from DSC measurements

Mechanical testing

Scale II - Neat cast resin

tensile tests

Scale III - Lamina (ply)

$\pm 45^\circ$ tensile tests \rightarrow ply shear behaviour

Scale IV - Laminate

4 point-bending

\rightarrow compressive failure strain

Thick laminates representative of composite parts for racing yachts

Degrees of conversion (w.r.t. uncured prepregs) – 92%, 95%, 100%

[Keryvin et al., CPB (2024)]

High stiffness and brittleness (low DOC) to ductility and lower stiffness (high DOC)

Lamina scale (III, Se75/IM2C) - Shear

Degrees of conversion (w.r.t. uncured prepregs) – 92%, 95%, 100%

[Keryvin et al., CPB (2024)]

The resin behaviour quantitatively transferred to the composite ply

Laminate scale (IV, Se75/IM2C)

Compressive strength of the ply in the laminate

Initial fibre misalignment
 $\phi_0 \sim 1^\circ$
(whatever the cure)

[Keryvin et al., CPB (2024)]

The difference in mechanical performance is found at all scales

Origins and uniqueness of this resin behaviour?

Unique case?

[Noordam et al., 1987]

Epikote epoxies (Shell)

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of the development of mechanical properties as a function of the degree of cure.

Figure 5. Mechanical properties of "EPIKOTE" 155/DMACM as a function of the degree of cure.

Known from a long time ago by epoxy chemists

Unique case?

[Marks et al., ACS AMI (2009)]

Dow Chemical, Epoxy R&D

« It is widely assumed that optimum properties of epoxy thermosets are achieved upon full cure »

Same belief as in our marine engineering circles

DGEBA + amines

[Marks et al., ACS AMI (2009)]

FIGURE 7. E vs α for DER 332-DETA, -IPDA, -MXDA, and -DDS thermosets.

Formation of covalent bonds \rightarrow constraints \rightarrow density decreases

E decreases with the degree of conversion

DGEBA + 3,3'-DDS

[Pramanik et al., Polym Engng Sci (2014)]

E' (RT) decreases with DOC

Summary and outlook

Unexpected effect of curing on the compressive strength of the composite ply

ANALYTICAL MODEL

UNDERSTANDING ESTIMATING

[Keryvin et al., CPB (2024)]

Complete curing does not give the optimal mechanical properties

Contributions to this work

- P.-Y. Méchin
- E. Fabing

- A. Le Palabe
- K. Mahé-Flahaut
- I. Pillin

See V. Keryvin et al., *Composites Part B* (2024) 287:11836